

PERSON-CENTERED EDUCATION AND CONDITIONS FOR ITS IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Person-centered learning technologies, in essence, involve the full development of all participants in the learning process. The article discusses about person-centered learning technologies and its implementation.

Keywords: *learning technologies, person-centered learning technologies, person-centered learning environment, professional skills, learning process.*

As we develop learning technologies, we implement person-centered learning technologies. This is because the individual is one of the main components of the National Training Program: the main subject and object of the training system, the consumer and producer of educational services. The personality of the learner is the goal of the entire education system, and remains an influential subject.

In a person-centered learning environment, we educators have a unique role and function in the learning process that is no less important than in the traditional system. If, in traditional education, we are in a supervisory role with the subject of knowledge and the textbook, which is the most competent source of knowledge, while in the new paradigm of education, we are in the role of independent active cognitive activity of learners in the role of organizer, competent advisor and assistant [Penny Thompson, 2018].

Person-centered education and conditions for its implementation

Basic control status of person-centered education	Terms of implementation
The identity of the learner is the goal of the	Ensuring a comfortable, conflict-free and safe environment for the full free and creative development of the learner, the realization of

<p>education system, the priority subject.</p>	<p>his natural potential. Acceptance by the educator of the learner: his or her goals, emotions, interests, views, attitudes, recognition of them as valuable qualities, trust in them, belief in his or her strengths and abilities.</p>
<p>Full development of all participants in the educational process: • Individualization and differentiation of the teaching process: Orientation to the individual trajectory of the student's personal development in accordance with the requirements of the STS in the field of vocational training.</p>	<p>The following should be taken into account in the development and implementation of educational technology: • the level of education in this field of knowledge and the general level of development of individual culture; • Psychological and physiological characteristics of the student: For each learner, the development of a curriculum that is individual to the curriculum is based on its individual characteristics and is finely adapted to its capabilities, its dynamic development under the influence of teaching; it helps him to understand himself, to clarify himself, to develop himself, and to realize his potential. Determining a learner's personal development and then objectively monitoring and diagnosing it to correct developmental prospects or extinctions. Develop and implement technology to develop the general pedagogical skills of the educator, self-development not only as a professional but also as an individual.</p>
<p>• Take into account the psychological, professional and personal characteristics and abilities of the student.</p>	<p>Build the learning process as a dialogue between educator and learner and focus it on collaborative program activities. • Responsibilities of the teacher: • Establish an equal position with the student: • not only to teach the student, but also to encourage him to develop, to create conditions for him to act independently: • Encourage learners to think independently, plan independently and suggest solutions to problems, and be prepared to evaluate and review results.</p>
<p>A dialogic approach that involves: • subjective interaction of participants in the learning process. • Increase the freedom of participants in the learning process • self-actualization and self-presentation.</p>	<p>To do this, do the following: • Conditional design: • Meaningful exploratory dialogue: • Incorporate learning tasks into the text of life problems: • Create conditions for learners to develop independent reading, self-determination, independence, self-realization and self-presentation skills.</p>
<p>Motivate the participants of the learning process.</p>	<p>This goal is achieved only when teaching and personal development have a vital and professional significance for the educator and the</p>

	learner, when there is a strong interest in this activity, when learning and development become a vital need of the individual. can be calculated.
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We use our professional skills not only to monitor the knowledge and skills of learners, but also to diagnose their activities in order to help us with our skilled efforts to overcome in a timely manner the difficulties that may arise in knowing and applying IFC we need to focus. This role is more complex than traditional education and requires a high level of skill from us.

We want to clarify the division of humanities - personal technologies, collaborative technologies and free education technologies as independent areas within the boundaries of person-centered educational technologies [Mishra P, Koehler M, 2006].

Human-personal education technologies are distinguished, first of all, by their humanitarian nature, psychotherapeutic orientation aimed at supporting and helping the individual. They embody the idea of full respect and love for the child, an optimistic belief in his creative power, and refrain from coercion.

Collaborative learning technologies promote democracy, equality, and cooperation in the subject-subject relationship between educator and child. The teacher and the student are in a collaborative, collaborative environment, working together to develop goals, content, and assess.

Free upbringing educational technologies focus on providing the child with free choice and independence in large or small areas of his or her life activities. The child, in making the choice, goes to the outcome not under external influence, but through his inner call, and best performs the subject's position.

Person-centered learning technologies, in essence, involve the full development of all participants in the learning process. This is not only a differentiated approach to teaching, taking into account the general level of intellectual development of the student and, in particular, his readiness for the subject, his abilities and capabilities, but also taking into account the psychological, professional and personal characteristics and abilities of the student.

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